

**BENUE JOURNAL OF
LIBRARY, MANAGEMENT AND
INFORMATION SCIENCE (BJLMIS)**

Vol. 10 No. 2 ISSN-2141-9361 December, 2020

**A PUBLICATION OF NIGERIAN LIBRARY
ASSOCIATION, BENUE STATE CHAPTER**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>Notes to contributors</i>	v
<i>Table of contents</i>	vii
<i>Editorial comments</i>	ix
Acquisition and Utilization of Serials in Federal University Libraries in South-East, Nigeria. Victoria N. Okafor, Ph.D and Prof. Raphael U. Ononogbo	1
Employee Recognition and Promotion as Factors of Librarians' Productivity in Academic Libraries in Imo State, Nigeria. Amarachi Perpetua Ezeogu and Nicholas Mfangu Tyonum	21
Assessment of Reading Culture among Inmates of Medium Security Custodian Centre, Katsina (Old): An Empirical Study Salisu, Shamwil Bala and Hassana Ibrahim	35
Technophobia and Use of Computer Technology among Non-Academic Staff of Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun, Ogun State. Osisanwo Temitope, Nwokike Obinna and Oloniruha Emmanuel	47
Appraisal of the Use of Gbenga Daniel Academic Library and Instructional Program among Undergraduates of Tai Solarin University of Education. Oluseun Mobolanle Sodipe	63
Availability and Utilization of Assistive Technologies in Polytechnic Libraries in Kogi State, Nigeria. Innocent, O. Adayi, Peter Odeh, Alice O. Odeh and Ozohu O. M. Audu	77

Technophobia and use of computer technology among the non-academic staff of Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State

By

Osisanwo Temitope, PhD

osisdetopsy@yahoo.com

Department of Library and Information Science,

Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun

Ogun State, Nigeria.

Nwokike Obinna, PhD

anwokike@biu.edu.ng

Department of Education, Library and Information Science programme

Benson Idahosa University

Edo State, Nigeria.

Oloniruha Emmanuel CLN

kingemmaa2000@gmail.com Kingemmaa2000@gmail.com

Center for learning resources

Redeemers College of Technology and Management

Ogun state

Abstract

The study investigated technophobia and use of computer technology among non-academic staff of Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. The purpose of the study is to examine the relationship between technophobia and use of computer technology. The study used a survey to carry out this research. A sample of 129 non-academic staff was selected from the registry department using total enumeration technique. The instrument used for the survey was questionnaire. Out of the one hundred and twenty nine (129) copies of the questionnaire that was self-administered, only 110 copies retrieved were found valid for data analysis. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics like percentages, frequency, mean, and inferential statistics like Pearson product moment correlation. Findings show that the available computer technologies include smart phones, laptops, desktop computer, photocopiers and printers. The level of technophobia among non-academic staff is low. There is a significant relationship between technophobia and the use of computer technology among non-academic staff. It was recommended that the university management should provide computer literacy training and opportunities to reduce the fear or anxiety among non-academic staff.

Introduction

Technology has become an integral part of our society. New technologies are continuously being introduced to both individual users and organisations as part of the operating systems. In many organisations, the employees tend to avoid new technologies when these are presented to them as their work tools. But, these organisations will continue to invest in new technologies in order to simplify tasks and stay competitive. This is because there are new and improved technologies developed for a device each day. Most new technologies simplify tasks by providing more functions in each device. On the other hand, these technologies may complicate life for users by making the use of each device harder to learn. Since the users struggle to learn to use or adapt to these new technologies in a timely manner, this creates a skill and knowledge gap. This in turn may slow the users adoption of new technologies and might be attributed to tension, anxiety, or apprehension. New technologies cannot improve organizational efficiency if employees avoid or choose not to use them all together. One of the most dynamic and innovative technologies is computer technology. Computer technology is currently used within many organizations including higher educational institutions as part of the operating systems.

Statement of the Problem

In the Nigerian education sector, computer technology has become so important that its knowledge and skill is necessary to succeed at many higher educational institutions. Many Nigerian universities have adopted the use of computer technology in their operations and for conducting examinations. Hence, students and staff that do not have

knowledge and skill in computers are likely to get further behind their peers who have such knowledge and skills. Some of the university students and staff may have developed a negative attitude towards the use of computer technology because they were affected by not passing required competency skills assessment or by other prior computer experiences. It is in line with the above that this study investigates technophobia and use of computer technology among non-academic staffs of Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun, Ogun State in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What are the various computer technology resources available in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?
- ii. What is the level of technophobia among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?
- iii. Which computer technologies are mostly used among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?
- iv. What are the problems affecting the use of computer technology among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between technophobia and the use of computer technology among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Literature Review

Across all organizational types, the employees physiological responses and attitudes should be considered whenever a new technology is introduced. Such technology-induced anxiety or fear is referred to as technophobia. Technophobia can be defined as fear/dislike of advanced technology or complex devices especially computers

(Achuonye & Ezekoka, 2011). It is an irrational fear or anxiety that individuals form as a response to a new technology that modifies or changes the routine of performing a certain task (Khasaweh, 2018; Osiceanu, 2015). It is a more general attitude often used to describe fear, discomfort, or anxiety toward technology of various forms (Salamzadeh, Mirakhori, Mobaraki & Targhi, 2013). It can be seen as a fear or dislike of technology in general or of particular devices like computers (Osisanwo, Ehiogae & Abdulsalam, 2019). This is different from the negative attitudes toward computers that entail personal beliefs and feelings about these technologies rather than ones emotional reaction towards using them (Simsek, 2011; Sam, Othman & Nordin, 2005).

Computer users who have computer anxiety often experience fear of the unknown and a feeling of frustration due to possible embarrassment, failure, and disappointment (Bolandifar & Noordin, 2015). Their anxiety is connected to the fear of the unfamiliar operations of the computer, fear of obsolescence and the thought that computers have a dehumanizing effect (Olatoye, 2009). Therefore, there is the need to disabuse the mind of such users from such fears and replace their misconceptions through confidence-building measures. Osisanwo, Ehiogae and Abdulsalam (2019) believe that providing the technical know-how and improving the intellectual ability to manipulate as well as discover the pedagogical power of the computer are important measures that can help reduce fear and anxiety among users. They also believe that increasing the use of a computer by guaranteeing access to a computer may result in improved computer experiences. But the increased use of the computer may not eliminate computer anxiety from all anxious users (Olatoye, 2009).

Also, the context in which the computer was first introduced, the introduction of new applications, past failures and successes with tasks are determining factors of computer anxiety (Ali, Yousefi & Yalda, 2012; Okore, 2015). For some scholars, self-efficacy and attitudes toward the use of a computer are believed to have an influence on computer anxiety (Igbaria, Zinatteli, Gagg & Cavaye, 2017). Studies have shown that computer anxiety is a predictor of perceived ease of use of automated library systems

by library staff in Nigerian universities (Uwaifo, 2008). The library staff exhibited a moderate level of computer anxiety.

Computer and other new technologies are currently used in the administrative operations of higher education institutions in Nigeria (Nwokoye & Uwajumoku, 2017). In these institutions, the use of computer technology is affecting the administrative operations. The use of computer technologies is determined by digital or computer literacy level of the administrators. Administrators use computer technology in the registration of students, identification cards, identification numbers, preparing school reports, disseminating announcements, letters for meetings, employment and so on. However, the use of computer technology in educational institutions is limited due to the lack of proper policies, inadequate technology facilities, erratic power supply and financial constraints (Margbalai, 2017; Ogunleye, 2017; Oketunji, Daniel, Okojie & Abdusalam, 2012; Oketunji, 2012; Adeyemi, 2013). Even when computers are available, administrators, instructors, and students rarely use them due to the lack of digital training and experience (Olatoye, 2009).

Methodology

This study was carried out using a cross-sectional survey research design. The study population was made up of all the non-academic staff of Tai Solarin University, Ijagun in Ogun State, Nigeria. The one hundred and twenty-nine (129) non-academic staff (male and female) was selected from the registry department using the total enumeration sampling technique. A total of one hundred and twenty-nine (129) copies of the questionnaire were self-administered but only 110 copies retrieved were found valid, representing a response rate of 85.27%. Data collection continued till all one hundred and twenty-nine (129) copies of the questionnaire retrieved were valid for data analysis. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics like percentages, frequency, mean scores, and inferential statistics like correlation.

Decision key: Mean score of $n \geq 2.6$ is high, 2.6 to 1.3 is moderate and $n \leq 1.3$ is low.

Results

Demographic Information of Respondents

Demographic features	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	62	56.4
Female	48	43.6
Age Range		
25yrs – 35yrs	33	30
36yrs – 45yrs	56	50.9
46yrs & above	21	19.1
Non-Academic Staff position		
Administrative Officers	42	38
Executive Officers	21	19
Accountants	28	25
Auditors	2	1
Confidential Secretaries	15	13
ICT staff	5	4
Total	110	100

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Results showed that 56.4% of the respondents were male while 43.6% of the respondents were female, which implies that the male respondents are more than the female respondents that

took part in the study. Based on their position, it could be depicted that 19% of the respondents that participated in the study were executive officers, 25% of the respondents were accountants and 16.4% of the respondents were administrative officers. Also, 13% were confidential secretaries and 4% of the respondents were ICT staff. It is therefore safe to conclude that all the respondents held non-academic positions.

Research Question 1: What are the various computer technologies available in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Table 2: Computer Technology Available

Computer Technologies	<i>Available</i>		<i>Unavailable</i>	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Smart phones	93	84.5	17	15.5
Laptops	91	82.7	19	17.3
Desktop computer	91	82.7	19	17.3
Photocopiers	86	78.2	24	21.8
Printers	75	68.2	35	31.8
DVD	69	62.7	41	37.3
Calculators	67	60.9	43	39.1
CD-ROMS	64	58.2	46	41.8
Scanner	62	56.4	48	43.6
Computer Software	61	55.5	49	44.5
Computer-mediated communication channels e.g. video chatting and instant messaging	60	54.5	50	45.5
E-reader devices	58	52.7	52	47.3

Projectors	55	50	55	50
Digital camera	50	45.5	60	54.5
Tablets/Palm Top	45	40.9	65	59.1

The result in table 2 revealed that 84.5% of the respondents affirmed that smartphones were available while 15.4% of the respondents had a contrary view. 82.7% of the respondents affirmed that laptops are available for use while 17.3% of the respondents had a contrary view. 82.7% of the respondents affirmed that desktop computers are available for use while 17.3% of the respondents had a contrary view. Based on the results above, it could be implied that among other computer technologies the respondents believed smartphones (84.5%), laptops (82.7%), desktop computers (82.7%), tablets (40.9%), and printers (68.2%) were more available.

Research Question 2: What is the level of technophobia among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Table 3: Level of Technophobia

Technophobia	<i>SA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>
I find it incompetent to say I dont like to use new equipment or technology	73	25	5	7	1.92
I feel comfortable when I use new equipment or technology	70	28	9	3	1.83
I feel excessive sweating while working with new equipment or technology	67	28	5	10	1.74
I find it difficult to learn how to use new technology	65	29	6	10	1.74
I feel forced to change my way of working because of new equipment or technology	64	35	10	1	1.53

I feel an irrational fear of new equipment or technology	58	32	6	14	1.51
I feel anxious while working with new equipment or technology	55	41	5	9	1.48
Im resistant to backup hard drives or organizing files on my computer	55	36	12	7	1.47
I avoid the use of new equipment and technology	53	38	12	7	1.41
I feel heart palpitation while working with new equipment or technology	45	16	34	15	1.35
I feel unskilled in the use of new equipment or technology	45	8	30	27	1.32
I find it difficult to complete computerized tasks	37	38	15	20	1.28
Overall Mean					18.58
Cumulative average Mean					1.55

Table 3 showed the level of technophobia among Non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. The results showed that the overall mean is $\bar{x}=18.58$ and the cumulative average mean is $\bar{x}=1.55$ which is an indication that there is a moderate level of technophobia among Non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. The mean scores of the items indicate that their level of technophobia is moderate. However, the mean score of 1.28 indicates their level of technophobia is low when completing computerized tasks. This implies that these respondents believe that it was less difficult to complete computerized tasks.

Research Question 3: Which computer technologies were used among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Table 4: Computer Technology Resources used

Computer Technology Resources	<i>Used</i>	<i>Not used</i>
Smart phones	93(84.5%)	17(15.4%)
Laptops	91(82.7%)	19(17.3%)
Desktop computer	91(82.7%)	19(17.3%)
Photocopiers	86(78.2%)	24(21.8%)
Printers	75(68.2%)	35(31.8%)
DVD	69(62.7%)	41(37.3%)
Calculators	67(60.9%)	43(39.1%)
CD-ROMS	64(58.2%)	46(41.8%)
Scanner	62(56.4%)	48(43.6%)
Computer Software	61(55.5%)	49(44.5%)
Computer mediated communication channels e.g. video chatting and instant messaging	60(54.5%)	50(45.5%)
E-reader devices	58(52.7%)	52(47.3%)
Projectors	55(50%)	55(50%)
Digital camera	50(50%)	60(54.5%)
Tablets/Palm Top	45(40.9%)	65(59.1%)

Table 4 revealed that 84.5% of the respondents indicated that they used smartphones and the remaining 15.4% had a contrary view. From the results, 82.7% of the respondents indicated that they used laptops and 17.3% of the respondents had a contrary view. Only 82.7% of the respondents indicated that they used desktop computers while 17.3% of the respondents indicated the contrary. Based on the ranking order of the results, it implied that the majority of the respondents used smartphones, laptops, desktop computers, tablets, and printers.

Research Question 4: What are the problems affecting computer technology usage among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State?

Table 5: Problems affecting the use of Computer Technology Usage

Problems	Agree	Disagree
Poor network	89 (80.8%)	21 (19.1%)
Lack of internet access	93 (84.5%)	17 (15.4%)
Inadequate power supply	95 (86.3%)	15 (13.7%)
High cost of airtime and internet subscription	93 (84.5%)	17 (15.4%)
High cost of purchase and maintaining the computer technology tools	83 (75.4%)	27 (24.5%)
Poor interconnectivity	94 (85.4%)	16 (14.5%)
Limited access to computer terminals	78 (70.9%)	32 (29.1%)
Limited time in accessing the internet	85 (78.1%)	25 (22.7%)
Poor management of the available ones	95 (86.4%)	15 (13.7%)
Lack of computer and IT skills	80 (72.7%)	30 (27.3%)

High level of illiteracy	95 (86.4%)	15 (13.5%)
Unconducive environment	80 (73%)	30 (27.3%)
Fear of computer use	69 (62.7%)	41 (37.3%)

The results of Table 5 reveal that 80.8% of the respondents affirmed that “poor network” was a problem affecting the use of computer technology while the remaining 19.1% of the respondents had a contrary view. 84.5% of the respondents indicated that “Lack of internet access” was a problem affecting the use of computer technology. Moreover, the major problems affecting the use of computer technology usage among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State were the poor network, lack of internet access, and inadequate power supply.

Research Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between technophobia and computer technology usage among non-academic staff

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Analysis

		Technophobia	Computer tech usage
Techno	Pearson Correlation	1	.715
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	110	110
Computer	Pearson Correlation	.715	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	

N

110

110

The table presents the relationship between technophobia and computer technology usage among non-academic staff. The table shows that a positive and strong relationship exists between technophobia and computer technology usage ($r = .715$). The relationship between the two variables is however revealed to be significant ($p < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship between technophobia and computer technology usage among non-academic staff.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one revealed the computer technologies that were available in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. Among the listed computer technologies that were indicated to be available by the respondents include, smartphones, laptops, desktop computers, tablets, and printers appeared to be more. This result corroborates the study findings of Osisanwo, Ehioghae, and Abdulsalam, (2019) that identified some of the available computer technology at Tai Solarin University of Education including laptops, desktop computers, and tablets, printers, scanners, and cameras, among others. The availability of computer technologies enables the administrative staff to perform their office work better since they have access to timely and accurate information (Nwokoye & Uwajumaju, 2017)

The findings of research question two revealed the level of technophobia among Non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. There is a moderate level of technophobia among the non-academic staff of this university. This implies that they were fewer non-academic staff with technophobia at the Tai Solarin University of Education. The finding corroborates studies like Nwokoye and Uwajumaju (2017) that found the administrative staff in two universities in south-east Nigeria were not technophobic. Their study revealed that administrative staff strongly disagreed that it is more difficult to work faster with the computer. It appears that staff no longer fear the use of computers in completing administrative tasks (Khasawneh, 2018).

The findings of research question three revealed the computer technologies that were used among non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. Among the listed computer technologies, smartphones, laptops, desktop computers, tablets, and printers had more usage than others. The result corroborates the findings of Nwokoye and Uwajumoju (2017) that administrative staff used computer technologies like smartphones, laptops, and desktop computers.

The findings of research question four revealed the problems affecting the use of computer technology among Non-academic staff in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. Among the major problems affecting the use of computer technology were poor network, lack of internet access, and inadequate power supply. Approximately 62.7% of the non-academic staff surveyed experienced some fear when they used computer technology in the university. However, it is believed that increasing their technical knowledge and experiences through training and mentoring will decrease their technophobia (Nwokoye & Uwajumoju, 2017). Technophobia can be prevented by early exposure to computer use (Achuonye & Ezekoka, 2011).

Based on the hypotheses tested, findings revealed that there is significant relationship between technophobia and computer technology usage among non-academic staff. This is because people who perceive computer technology as non-threatening were eager to adapt to new technologies. This finding corroborates studies that establish an association between technophobia and the use of computer technology (Ajayi, Olatokun & Tihamiyu, 2001; Achuonye & Ezekoka, 2011; Rosen & Weil, 1995). Rosen and Weil (1995) point out that technophobia could serve as an explanation for low levels of computer utilization.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the computer technology resources that were majorly available for use are smartphones laptops, desktop computers, tablets, and printers. It was concluded that there is a low level of technophobia among non-academic staff. Based on the findings, the following was recommended:

- i. The management should provide more or adequate facilities that will encourage or promote the use of computers and other technology tools among non-academic staff
- ii. There should be a policy by the university management to mandate all concerned non-academic staff to always use new technologies to carry out their daily activities
- iii. The management should continually organize a training and re-training program that will encourage the use of computers and other technology tools
- iv. There should be adequate provision of internet services by the university management
- v. The management should also provide un-interrupted power supply that will encourage the use of computer technology

Reference

- Achuonye, K. A. & Ezekoka, G. K. (2011). Technophobia among female undergraduate students: a challenge to the attainment of the MDGs in Nigeria. *British Journal of Educational Research*. 1 (1), 49-57.
- Adeyemi, N. N. (2013). *New technology and developing countries: the Nigeria experience*. In Brown, K. R (Ed), *The Challenge of information technology*. 69-98 Amsterdam: North Hothead publishing.
- Ajayi, A., Olatokun, W. M. & Tihamiyu, M. A. (2001). Computer anxiety, phobia, obsession, and work stress at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 11 (2): 125-138
- Ali, A., Yousefi, A. & Yalda, J. (2012). Dealing with teachers technophobia in the classroom. *Advances in Asian Social Science (AASS)* 452, 2 (2), 2167-6429.
- Bolandifar, S. & Noordin, N. (2015). Computer anxiety and attitude towards using the internet in English language classes among Iranian postgraduate student teachers. *Journal of Social Science and Humanities*. 23 (2), 355-374
- Igbaria, M., Zinatteli, N., Gagg, P., & Cavaye, A. (2017). Personal computing accepting factors in small firms: a structural equation model. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(3), 279-305.
- Khasawneh, O. Y. (2018). Technophobia: Examining its hidden factors and defining it. *Technology in society*. 13: 60.
- Margalai, M. A. (2017). Factors affecting information technology transfer in developing countries. *LIBRI*, 37 (5), 39-245
- Nwokoye, E. S. & Uwajumogu, N. R. (2017). Digital media and capacity building of non-academic staff in Nigerian universities: insights from Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra state and Federal University Ndufu-Alike, Ikwo, Ebonyi state. In J. O. Ezeokana, I. V. Dunu & C. E. Nwafor (Eds), *New media and capacity building in developing economies*(Pp. 1-15). Nigeria: Fab Anieh Nig. Ltd Awka
- Ogunleye, G. O. (2017). Automating the federal university libraries in Nigeria to a state of the art. *African Journal of Libraries, Archives and Information Sciences*, 7 (1); 71-79.
- Oketunji, I. (2012). Application of information technologies in Nigeria: problems and prospects. *A paper presented at the 10th Biennial Conference of the National Association of Library and Information Science Educators*. Pg. 7-20.
- Oketunji, I., Daniel, J. O., Okojie, V. O. & Abdusalam, R. (2012). 40 years of library and information services to the Nation. *A Compendium of papers presented at the 40th National Conferences and AGM of the Nigerian Library Association*.
- Okore, A. M. (2015). The challenges of information and communication technology (ICT) for Nigerian academic libraries. *Global Review of Library and Information Science*, 1(1), 84-93.
- Olatoye, R. A. (2009). Influence of computer anxiety and knowledge on computer utilization of senior secondary school students. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 7(3), 1269-1288.
- Osiceanu, M. (2015). Psychological implications of modern technologies; "technophobia" versus "technophilia", *Social Behaviour Science*. 180, 1137-1144.

- Osisanwo, T., Ehioghae, M. & Abdulsalam, T. (2019). Information Impact: *Journal of information and knowledge management*, 10 (2), 18-38.
- Popoola, S. O. P. (2012). Faculty awareness about the library, information products and services in Nigerian universities, *Gateway Library Journal*, 4(1&2), 1-11.
- Rosen, L. D. & Weil, M. M. (1995). Computer availability, computer experience and technophobia among public school teachers. *Computer in Human Behaviour*. 11(1): 9-31.
- Salamzadeh, Y., Mirakhori, A. R., Mobaraki, L. & Targhi, Z. H. (2013). Technophobia in universities: to be or not to be, this is the problem. *AWER Proceedia. Information Technology and Computer Science*. 3, 186-190.
- Sam, H. K., Othman, A. E. & Nordin, Z. S. (2005). Computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety and attitudes towards the internet: a study among undergraduates in UNIMAS. *Educational Technology & Society*, 8(4), 205-219.
- Simsek, A. (2011). The relationship between computer anxiety and computer self-efficacy. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 2(3), 177-187
- Uwaifo, S. O. (2008). Computer anxiety as a predictor of librarians perceived ease of use of automated library systems in Nigerian university libraries. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*. 18 (2), 147